

Characterization of the High-Energy Tail of the ^{235}U Fission Gamma Spectrum Using Stilbene Spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

The high-energy tail ($E > 10$ MeV) of the ^{235}U fission gamma spectrum is vital for reactor heat deposition and material damage calculations, despite the fact that only one measurement exists. This paper reports the first comprehensive experimental characterization of this high-energy tail. Measurements were conducted at the LR-0, VR-1, and JSI TRIGA reactors using a stilbene spectrometer. A key finding is the excellent consistency in the spectral shape observed above 11 MeV across all three, geometrically different, reactor environments. This consistency validates the measurement procedure and confirms the dominance of fission gammas in this region. Comparisons to MCNP6.2 calculations demonstrate that while the recent ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries reasonably reproduce the spectral shape, other libraries, such as ENDF/B-VII.1 and JEFF-4.0, lack the necessary data, and JENDL-5 exhibits significant divergence. These findings provide crucial, previously unavailable data for validating and improving transport calculations.

Keywords: fission, gamma, stilbene

1. INTRODUCTION

A precise characterization of the fission gamma-ray spectrum from the neutron-induced fission of ^{235}U is crucial for both fundamental nuclear physics and a range of practical applications. The high-energy portion of this spectrum, typically defined as energies above 10 MeV, is of particular interest as it directly probes the de-excitation of the most energetic fission fragments formed moments after scission [1], [2]. These high-energy gamma rays originate from transitions between nuclear states at very high excitation energies, providing a unique window into the structure of neutron-rich nuclei far from stability and the mechanisms governing the sharing of excitation energy between fragment pairs [1].

From a practical standpoint, the high-energy gamma rays from fission are primarily important for heat deposition and radiation damage in nuclear reactor components. As these photons are highly penetrating, they can deposit their energy far from the fission site, impacting the thermal-hydraulic behavior of the core and the structural integrity of materials. Non-negligible is also the fact that even a small flux of high-energy gammas can induce secondary reactions, such as (γ, n) or (γ, p) , in structural and shielding materials. Accurate data in this region, therefore, support improved assessments of component lifetimes and facilitate benchmarking of transport calculations against experimental measurements.

There are relatively sufficient measurements of the fission gamma spectrum from the fission of ^{235}U , but only one covers the range above 10 MeV [3], [4]. This work presents the first measurements above this

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energy, performed on three reactor facilities (LR-0, VR-1, and JSI TRIGA MARK II), and is currently focused on the shape of the spectrum. The next goal is to make these measurements absolute.

2. METHODS

2.1. LR-0 reactor

The LR-0 reactor is a light-water moderated, pool-type research reactor operated by the Centrum výzkumu Řež. Its core is composed of six hexagonal fuel assemblies in radial cut identical to VVER-1000 fuel. In the current experiment, 3.6% enriched fuel was used. In a core similar to the core used in the current experiment, having the same geometry but with fuels that have only 3.3% enrichment, a benchmark reference neutron field has been identified. The core is described in [5].

2.2. VR-1 reactor

The VR-1 reactor is a light-water, pool-type research reactor operated by the Czech Technical University in Prague, primarily dedicated to education, training, and experimental research. Its core is composed of standard IRT-4M fuel assemblies with low-enriched uranium (19.7% ²³⁵U) dispersed in an aluminum matrix and clad with aluminum alloy. The core is described in [6].

2.3. JSI TRIGA MARK II reactor

The TRIGA MARK II research reactor at the Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) is a pool-type reactor with a maximum steady-state power of 250 kW. The reactor core has a cylindrical configuration and consists of cylindrical fuel elements with stainless steel cladding. The fuel material is a homogeneous mixture of uranium and ZrH with 12 wt.% uranium and 20 % enrichment. There are 66 mm of graphite reflector and 104 mm of stainless steel above each fuel element. The fuel elements are inserted into a water pool. The core is described in [7].

2.4. Stilbene spectrometry

Measurement was performed using a stilbene scintillator connected to the NGA-01 spectrometer. The dimensions of the stilbene crystal were 45 × 45 mm (diameter × height). Details about the spectrometer are available in [8]. Neutron/gamma discrimination was performed using pulse shape discrimination. Details about the method are available in [9]. The gamma spectrum was then obtained from the measured pulse height distribution by deconvolution using Maximum Likelihood Estimation [10] with a validated response matrix [11].

2.5. Measurement geometry

The gamma spectra were measured in three different reactors, each with a significantly different geometry and power. Therefore, the measurement geometries differed significantly. They are described in the following subsections. For each reactor, two measurements were performed: one during operation and one during shutdown to assess background radiation from natural sources, long-lived fission products, and cosmic muons. The pulse-height spectra from the background measurement were subtracted from the operational measurement before deconvolution.

2.5.1. LR-0 reactor

This core was used due to the very low gamma background activity, which would otherwise have had a negative influence on the scintillation measurement. However, the geometry is not identical to the core where the benchmark reference neutron field was identified [12]. It was shown that the neutron and gamma spectrum shapes in the reference (3.3%) and 3.6 % core are very similar [13].

The gamma measurement was realized in the center of the dry central channel at an axial level of 22 cm above the beginning of the fuel fissile column, which is approximately half of the critical level. During the experiment, 15 measurements were performed, totaling 50 hours. These measurements were evaluated in a single spectrum up to 13 MeV. The average reactor power was in the order of miliWatts, which corresponds to the gamma flux of $1E3 \text{ cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ in the measurement position. The background

spectrum was measured immediately after the reactor shut down. For the LR-0 reactor, the background is not negligible; more details are available in [5]. The measured background signal is always subtracted.

2.5.2. VR-1 reactor

The gamma spectrum in the VR-1 reactor was measured above the water level. The detector was mounted on the aluminum table, with its center 86 cm above the water level. The height of the water above the fuel is 306 cm. The measurement took nearly 19 hours at an average power level of 650 Watts. The background spectrum was measured immediately after the reactor shut down. The background share is lower than in the LR-0 reactor but can reach 60% at 14 MeV. The measured background signal is always subtracted.

2.5.3. JSI TRIGA MARK II reactor

The gamma spectrum for the JSI Triga Mark-II reactor was measured approximately 120 cm above the water level, with a water column height of 480 cm. The measurement took 10 h and was realized at a power of 250 kW. The background was measured immediately after reactor shutdown. It is worth noting that, due to the high power, the background is lowest in the studied case; the share is about 50% at 14 MeV, and the background is subtracted.

2.6. Calculations

Calculations were performed in the MCNP6.2 code [14] using different nuclear data libraries, namely ENDF/B-VIII.1 [15], ENDF/B-VIII.0 [16], ENDF/B-VII.1 [17], JEFF-4.0 [18], JEFF-3.3 [19], and JENDL-5 [20]. All calculations were performed in eigenvalue mode. For the LR-0 reactor, because the detector is at the reactor center, the track-length estimator (F4) tally was used. For the VR-1 and JSI TRIGA MARK II reactors, the detector was far from the core; thus, the point detector tally (F5) was used. To reproduce the detector response, all calculated spectra were convolved with the detector's resolution matrix, which represents its Gaussian energy resolution.

3. RESULTS

The measured gamma spectra are shown in Figure 1. For direct comparison, spectra were normalized to one in the energy range of 11-12 MeV. It can be seen that above 11 MeV, all spectra are identical within uncertainties. The differences between spectra for energies below 11 MeV are caused by a different share of prompt gammas from radiative capture or inelastic scattering, which is the dominant source of gammas in this energy range. Each reactor contains different materials and their distribution, leading to these significant differences. Above 11 MeV, the share of gammas from radiative capture or inelastic scattering is negligible. The identity of the spectra above 11 MeV confirms the validity of the measurement procedure.

The low-energy part of the γ -spectrum (below 6 MeV) reflects the measurement position and thus the extent of shielding by water or other materials. A steep increase in the low-energy region is observed for the detector placed directly at the center of the LR-0 reactor core. In the VR-1 reactor, where 306 cm of water is present, the spectrum shows only a slight increase toward lower energies. For the TRIGA reactor, with 480 cm of water and an additional 17 cm of graphite and stainless steel shielding, the low-energy part becomes almost flat. These observations also confirm the validity and consistency of the measurement procedure.

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Figure 1. Measured gamma spectra of different reactors. Spectra were normalized to one between 11-12 MeV.

For comparison, fission gamma spectra in different nuclear data libraries are depicted in Figure 2. Fission gamma spectra in ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 are identical. Significant discrepancies can be observed, comprising energy and spectrum shape. Spectra shapes, not absolute flux values, are relatively identical below 5 MeV, but above this value, trends are very different.

Figure 2. Fission emission gamma spectra in different nuclear data libraries.

As can be seen from Figure 2, a reasonable comparison of the high-energy tail of fission gamma spectra can be done only for ENDF/B-VIII.0/ENDF/B-VIII.1, but for illustration, all libraries were compared for the case of the LR-0 reactor, as it is a reference neutron field with an identity of prompt fission neutron spectrum above 6 MeV [9]. It is shown in Figure 3. In this figure, calculations are normalized per source neutron, and the measurement is normalized in the interval 1-5 MeV to the average of all calculations, because all calculations have the same shape and almost the same magnitude in this energy region. As expected from Figure 2, JENDL-5 diverges above 8.5 MeV, and it is several orders of magnitude above the measurement. In the case of ENDF/B-VII.1 and JEFF-4.0, in which fission gamma stops at 8 MeV, there is still a non-negligible gamma flux above 11 MeV. This is noteworthy because 11 MeV is approximately the energy above which very little gamma from neutron radiative capture is expected. This gamma radiation originates mainly from reactions induced by epithermal and fast neutrons and shows an unexpectedly high intensity that should be examined in more detail.

Figure 3. Gamma spectra comparison for the LR-0 reactor. Calculations normalized per source neutron; measurement normalized in the interval of 1-5 MeV to the average of all calculations.

Another comparison is shown in Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6. These figures show a comparison of measured and calculated data for the ENDF/B-VIII.0/ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries, with normalization in the energy interval of 11-12 MeV. It is the same normalization interval as in the comparison of measurements in Figure 1. Because the prompt fission gamma spectrum is identical in both libraries, differences in the calculated spectra arise from other interactions, predominantly from radiative capture. It can be seen that in the case of LR-0 and VR-1 reactors, the shapes of calculated spectra above 11 MeV are identical, and in the case of TRIGA reactors, in the energy interval of 11-14 MeV, the shape of the calculated spectrum is within uncertainties, but above 14 MeV, it differs from the measurement.

Figure 4. Gamma spectra comparison for the LR-0 reactor. Calculations were normalized in the interval of 11-12 MeV to the measurement.

Figure 5. Gamma spectra comparison for VR-1 reactor. Calculations were normalized in the interval of 11-12 MeV to the measurement.

Figure 6. Gamma spectra comparison for JSI TRIGA MARK II reactor. Calculations were normalized in the interval of 11-12 MeV to the measurement.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Gamma spectra in various reactors were measured, showing excellent agreement in the spectrum shape above 11 MeV in all cases. The spectra of VR-1 and TRIGA reactors are affected by the water reflector between the core and the detector; however, water is not an effective shielding material for gammas, resulting in a low effect on the shape of the high-energy tail of the reactor spectrum. The paper focused on the comparison of spectrum shapes, showing good agreement for the ENDF/B-VIII.0/ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries. Future work will focus on the absolute comparison of measured and calculated spectra.

Future work will also focus on the study of the share of non-fission gammas above 11 MeV, as calculations using different libraries indicate a relatively high share. Above 11 MeV, this gamma radiation should be negligible, as it would predominantly involve radiative capture by higher-energy neutrons, but the probability is several orders of magnitude lower than that for thermal radiative capture (as reflected in the shape of the radiative capture cross section).

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